

Shiyan Natalia,

(Istomina) PhD in Biology,

Department of Molecular Biology, Lomonosov Moscow State University

Dashkevich Olga,

C. Sc. (Med.), associate professor

Department of Outpatient Therapy,

Preventive Medicine and General Medical Practice, Ryazan State Medical University

Yakubovskaya Alina

C. Sc. (Med.), associate professor

Department of Outpatient Therapy,

Preventive Medicine and General Medical Practice, Ryazan State Medical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13369161>

RESEARCH RESULTS. POST-COVID-19 SYNDROME

Abstract

Purpose of the study: The aim of the present scientific paper is to evaluate the prevalence of various post-coronavirus infection conditions and the impact on physical health in patients. In addition, the research study strives to profoundly analyse each of potential manifestations taking into consideration severity of the disease, presence of polymorbidity, time interval from an approximate period of infection.

Materials and Methods

For the current research paper, a group of 253 subjects has been selected. In this group, there are 187 female patients and 66 male patients at the age from 18 to 85 years old. The choice is determined by the objective of analysing the physical state of those people who were infected by the coronavirus infection once and experienced a range of common symptoms.

On the basis of the severity of the infection in the onset phase of COVID-19, the subjects have been divided into two separate groups. Group 1 largely encompassed those individuals who accessed the health services with a mild course ($n=133$). As for Group 2, it predominantly included people with moderate to severe COVID-19 ($n=120$).

Each group has been additionally subdivided into two subgroups depending on the time interval after the onset period of the infectious disease. The first two subgroups named 1A and 2A largely included those who were closely examined up to three months after the acute period took place. The other two subgroups named 1B and 2B consisted of the subjects who were examined three months after the coronavirus infection.

A multistage telephone interview has been carried out among the listed above groups of patients. The method that has been applied in the research was recognised to identify a possible presence of symptoms. Furthermore, the outpatient medical records of those who consulted general practitioners (GP) or specialist doctors (SD) have been carefully studied.

Conclusion

The research has revealed that the development of the Syndrome cannot be dependent on the severity of the acute disease. Therefore, it can occur either as the consequence of a mild, moderate or severe course. It is curious to notice that more comorbidities are expected to be found as the result of the last category.

The overwhelming number of patients who recovered from the infection found themselves complaining of new onset diseases. The analysis has found that they can be manifested in the disrupt of the normal functioning of the central nervous system (CNS). In addition, Cardiovascular Diseases (CVD) and Bronchopulmonary System Diseases (BPD) have been identified as the most frequent long-term conditions after the infection. The individuals of the other category who experienced severe symptoms demonstrated that they predominantly suffered from comorbidities.

It is worth mentioning that each individual whether experiencing mild, moderate or severe symptoms, should get proper extended care during the first twelve weeks after the onset period of the disease. Achieving complete recovery of individuals is an essential part of the fight against the disease. On the other hand, the lack of any follow-up care for a prolonged period can cause a number of negative conditions, hence worsen the well-being of a person.

Keywords: coronavirus infection, COVID-19, post-COVID-19 Syndrome, central nervous system disorder, comorbidities, bronchopulmonary system disorder, cardiovascular system disorder

Introduction

As is well known, as the number of cases of the infection increases, more patients appear to recover. On the other hand, individuals face numerous physical conditions of any severity, which directly influences the well-being and reduces the quality of life of an individual [1]. The symptom complex that acquired the name

Post-COVID-19 Syndrome is considered one of such consequences that usually develops after the onset phase. It is included in The International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision (ICD-10), and has the category code of U09.9.

The Syndrome can be defined as a set of signs and symptoms arises either during, or after the onset phase of

COVID-19 and continues on average for more than three months. It is essential to note that an individual can be diagnosed with the condition if alternative diagnoses are completely excluded [2]. However, a number of cases when a patient suffers from such symptoms have been recorded four weeks after the onset period.

Contemporary researchers tend to distinguish the following forms of post-acute COVID 19 [3]:

1. subacute, or Ongoing Symptomatic Infection that can be diagnosed when a person experiences the common symptoms for around four to twelve weeks after the onset period.

2. chronic, or Post-COVID-19 Syndrome that manifests itself in the persistence of characteristic conditions beyond around twelve weeks from the onset phase. An additional feature of the type is that its symptoms cannot be explained by any alternative diagnosis.

It is worth noticing that the clinical manifestations, i.e. residual effects of the viral infection, can remain as a consequence of the infectious process. Furthermore, it cannot be excluded that patients in this group constitute the vast number of patients.

Although there are numerous research studies carried out in this particular field, many questions concerning the reasons that influence the development of the Syndrome remain [4-9]. The role of age, gender or polymorbidity affecting the formation of the clinical condition deserve further study. Overall, the considerable variability in the frequency of symptoms detected can be closely related both to differences in the time interval and to the study of the frequency of conditions when intensity of treatment, disease severity or presence of comorbid pathology are not taken into consideration.

Materials and Methods. Study Design

For the research analysis, a group of 253 people consisting of 187 women and 66 men at the age from 18 to 85 has been randomly selected from an unspecified number of patients. Each individual involved in the study has previously signed informed consent to participate in it and kindly provide the necessary data.

The approval of the local ethical committee has been obtained as well (Minutes no. 9 dated 05.04.2021).

The diagnosis of the disease was confirmed by identification of SARS-COV-2 virus RNA by PCR / detection of IgM class antibodies to the virus in 190 (75%) patients during the acute period or identification of IgG class antibodies in 45 (17.8%) during the period of recollection. The diagnosis of the infection was not confirmed in 18 (7.1%) patients, but the development of a characteristic clinical picture of it after close contact with other patients with SARS-CoV-2 makes it possible to conclude that the disease commenced to progress in them.

The selected group of individuals has been divided into two categories of patients on the basis of the severity of the course of the infection that are as follows:

Group 1 encompassing those subjects who underwent a mild course (n=133). In the patients, the disease

proceeded as acute respiratory infection; therefore, hospitalisation was not required.

Group 2 included the patients who experienced a moderate to severe course (n=120) and their disease took the form of pneumonia (lung involvement was assessed as 25-80% as Computed Tomography (CT) Scan determined). Hence, many patients required hospitalisation.

Each group has been additionally subdivided into two separate subgroups – A and B – on the grounds of the time interval after the onset period. In Subgroup A, each patient was closely examined up to twelve weeks after the acute phase of COVID-19. Subgroup B entirely consisted of the individuals who were thoroughly examined three months after the period.

In the present research paper, the method of a multi-stage telephone survey that is a sequence of questions has been applied. Collecting outpatient medical records of those patients who at some point consulted their general practitioners (GP) or specialist doctors (SD), such as pulmonologists, cardiologists, gastroenterologists, endocrinologists, etc. have been selected as additional methods for this study.

The survey has been carried out with the use of a questionnaire that included the following data: sex; age; time interval after the disease; diagnosis during the acute period; method used to confirm the diagnosis during the onset phase; recommended treatment (antiviral drugs, antibiotics, glucocorticosteroids or anticoagulants); complaints lasting up to 3 months and more after the disease (such as fatigue, memory problems, headache, insomnia, shortness of breath, cough, chest pain, fever, tachycardia, heart pain, kidney disorder, arterial hypertension, anosmia/dysgeusia, myalgia, arthralgia, liver disorder, alopecia, etc.).

Dysfunction of cellular immunity has been additionally considered as a symptom of Post-COVID-19 Syndrome. The questioning has been conducted at various times after the disease, but the duration of certain clinical manifestations has been specified.

The statistical analysis of the study results has been performed with Statistica 10.0 software (StatSoft Inc., USA) using standard statistical methods. Differences between the groups have been considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

The obtained results of the conducted research study are presented in Tables 1 and 2. The patients with clinical manifestations in whom symptoms lasted up to three months have been referred to the group with Post-acute COVID-19 Syndrome (i.e., syndrome with clinical signs up to three months). The duration of more than twelve weeks has been agreed to be considered as Post-COVID-19 Syndrome.

Table 1 shows the number of patients who did not have any typical symptoms of the coronavirus infection and, accordingly, the presence of any was not found in various time periods.

Table 1

Number of Symptoms	Group 1 (n=133)		Group 2 (n=120)	
	Subgroup 1A (n=52)	Subgroup 1B (n=81)	Subgroup 2A (n=45)	Subgroup 2B (n=75)
No symptoms	7 (13,5)	34 (42)	3 (6,7)	13 (17,3)**
1 symptom	22 (42,3)	18 (22,2)	7 (15,6)*	19 (25,3)
2 symptoms	10 (19,2)	11 (13,6)	11 (24,4)	17 (22,7)
3 and more symptoms	13 (25)	18 (22,2)	24 (53,3)*	36 (34,7)

Note * - $p < 0,01$, when compared with the value in the Group 1; ** - $p < 0,001$, when compared with the value in the Group 1.

Table 2 reflects the most frequent symptoms that the selected patients complained about during various periods of follow-up, n (%).

Table 2

Clinical Symptom	Group 1 (n=133)		Group 2 (n=120)	
	Subgroup 1A (n=52)	Subgroup 1B (n=81)	Subgroup 2A (n=45)	Subgroup 2B (n=75)
Fatigue	22 (42,3)	32 (39,5)	34 (75,6)**	48 (64)
Cognitive disorders	4 (7,7)	11 (13,6)	16(35,6)**	13 (17,3)***
Headache	2 (3,8)	5 (6,2)	9 (20)*	7 (9,3)
Insomnia	3 (5,8)	3 (3,7)	7 (15,6)	8 (10,7)
Shortness of breath	8 (15,4)	9 (11,1)	23 (51,1)**	24 (32)
Cough	8(15,4)	8 (9,9)	15 (33,3)	16 (21,3)
Fever	3 (5,8)	7 (8,6)	4 (8,9)	6 (8)
Arterial hypertension	3 (5,8)	6 (7,4)	7 (15,6)	5 (5,9)
Tachycardia	4 (7,7)	2 (2,5)	11 (24,4)*	14 (8,7)
Arthralgia	3 (5,8)	9 (11,1)	8 (17,8)	15 (20)
Liver disorder	0	3 (3,7)	1 (2,2)	2 (2,7)
Intestinal disorder	1 (1,9)	4 (4,9)	2 (4,4)	0
Kidney disorder	0	1 (1,2)	2 (4,4)	1 (1,3)
Anosmia/Dysgeusia	4 (7,7)	9 (11,1)	3 (6,7)	6 (8)
Alopecia	3 (5,8)	1 (1,2)	4 (8,9)	2 (2,7)
Other symptoms	1 (1,9)	0	2 (4,4)	1 (1,3)

Note *** - $p < 0,05$, when compared with the value of subgroup 2A patients; * - $p < 0,05$, when compared with the value in the group 1A patients; ** - $p < 0,001$, when compared with the value of subgroup 1A patients.

The achieved results show that the characteristic symptoms the Syndrome have been found and further recorded in the individuals of Subgroup 1A (45/52 (86.5%)) and Subgroup 2A (42/45 (93.3%)). That is to say, any negative conditions were absent in 7 (13.5%) and 3 (6.7%) subjects.

The research study has additionally found that any characteristic symptoms were completely absent in 34 (42%) individuals of Subgroup 1B and in 13 (17.3%) subjects of Subgroup 2B ($p < 0.001$) after twelve weeks after the onset of COVID-19. Meanwhile, at least one clinical condition has been recorded in 47/81 (58%) people of Subgroup 1B and 62/75 (82%) patients of Subgroup 2B. Furthermore, A. Carfi et al. [10] mentioned that around 87% of patients had some symptoms at hospital discharge. Thus, it is possible to claim that the results of the study are consistent with the literature data.

It has been recorded during the analysis that the frequency of the conditions after recovery, depending on the follow-up periods reported in the literature does not differ significantly from the present research with few exceptions [3, 11, 12]. Among the most frequent symptoms in individuals who had a mild course for approximately three months after the onset phase there were fatigue, dyspnea as well as cough.

Those symptoms have been found in the individuals who had moderate to severe coronavirus infection. However, pneumonia became a consequence for the further disrupt of the normal functioning of the central nervous system (CNS). Among these disorders, it is possible to enumerate cognitive disorders, headache and insomnia. Furthermore, a moderate or severe course has been reported to affect cardiovascular health and hence cause related diseases such as arterial hypertension and tachycardia. It is worth noticing that arthralgia has been additionally found as one of the most spread disorders of other systems. Nevertheless, the cause of circulatory system involvement still remains rather unclear and deserves further careful study. Direct cardiotoxic effect of COVID-19 as well as plaque rupture and coronary thrombosis, effects of proinflammatory cytokines, coagulopathy are currently discussed; cardiotoxic effect of drugs used in the treatment of the disease cannot be excluded either. Neurotoxic effects of the disease on both the central and peripheral nervous system, effects of proinflammatory cytokines, autoimmune factors, hypoxaemia are considered to be the main causes of the disorders of nervous system (NS) [13-18]. As for functional gastrointestinal (FGID) or urinary tract disorders (UTD), Table 2 shows that they are quite uncommon after recovery. As the period after the acute phase passed, the frequency of symptoms experienced decreases, however a statistically significant difference has been recorded only with respect to cognitive disorders. After 8-12 months after the onset phase of COVID-19, the overwhelming number of symptoms either disappears altogether, or decreases in intensity. With very few exceptions, anosmia / dysgeusia does not always disappear, even twelve months after the onset phase.

A comparative analysis of clinical conditions after acute respiratory infection (i.e., a mild course) and pneumonia (i.e., moderate to severe) indicates that individual clinical manifestations were significantly more common

after pneumonia in the first twelve weeks after the onset phase. On the contrary, fatigue, cognitive disorders, headache, dyspnea as well as tachycardia were found to be less frequent. Those individuals who were examined three months after the acute period demonstrated less pronounced differences. It cannot be excluded that more severe disease sequela in the first three months after pneumonia may be due not only to severe forms of organ and system damage caused by coronavirus, but due to active use of medicines affecting the health of an individual.

Among rare sequelae in people with the Syndrome can be included such clinical conditions as weight loss / gain, development of autoimmune hepatitis (AH) six months after the onset phase and intrauterine fetal death (IFD).

When cellular immune dysfunction is included in the list of clinical conditions of the Syndrome, its development is independent of the severity of the course. That is, its emergence can be found both in mild and moderate to severe COVID-19. However, it is obvious that in the last category of cases, more symptoms prevail.

As for gender differences, fatigue after a mild course is two times more frequent in women the first three months after the acute phase rather than in men has been traced. After moderate to severe case, shortness of breath is more common in men (72.8% vs 44.1%, $p < 0.05$) in the first three months after the disease, thereafter the incidence of shortness of breath decreases in both men and women.

Distribution of patients by age made it possible to find that the frequency of fatigue and dyspnea increases with age. This is probably determined not only by damage to the bronchopulmonary and nervous systems, but by damage to the cardiovascular system.

Comorbidities have been detected in 33/52 (63.5%) subjects with a mild course within up to twelve weeks after the onset phase, and in 62/81 (76.6%) within more than twelve weeks. In the category of subjects with a moderate to severe course, comorbidities have been detected in 41/45 (91.1%) and 64/75 (85.3%) in people within up to 12 weeks or more after the onset phase. Comorbidity probably determines the severity of the course, as it has been more frequently traced in the subjects from Group 2 ($p < 0.01$). Most other people, were diagnosed with cardiovascular disease, diabetes mellitus, obesity, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Numerous researchers additionally note that comorbidities worsen the prognosis.

Conclusion

The present scientific paper has revealed that the occurrence of the Syndrome is not determined by the severity of the disease during the onset period, and it may arise both in a mild course and moderate to severe COVID-19 cases. Nevertheless, those with more severe cases are likely to experience a greater number of symptoms, according to the results obtained during the analysis.

After recovering from the coronavirus infection, bronchopulmonary, cardiovascular and the central nervous systems are predominantly affected in the development of Post-COVID-19 Syndrome. The conditions may

cause fatigue, cognitive issues, tachycardia, dyspnea, headache. The prevalence of common symptoms decreases with time after the onset phase, and as the time passes, one finds themselves feeling better. Thus, it can be claimed that both the frequency and severity of symptoms decrease with time.

It has been additionally revealed that among the rare sequelae in individuals with the Syndrome are weight loss and gain, occurrence of Autoimmune Hepatitis (AH) six months after the onset phase and Intrauterine Fetal Death (IFD).

Comorbidities are closely intertwined with the severity of the course of the disease in the acute phase, as it is more often examined in individuals with the development of pneumonia. Furthermore, it is necessary that patients who have recovered from COVID-19 receive ongoing medical support in the first twelve weeks and beyond, which is provided by a team of specialists, so as to ensure both full recovery and enhancement of their quality of life.

References:

1. Klitzman R.L. Needs to Prepare for "Post-COVID-19 Syndrome". *Am J Bioeth.* 2020;20(11):4–6. DOI: 10.1080/15265161.2020.1820755.
2. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence. COVID-19 rapid guideline: managing the long-term effects of COVID-19. (Electronic resource.) URL: <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/ng188> (access date: 20.11.2021).
3. Nalbandian A., Sehgal K., Gupta A. et al. Post-acute COVID-19 syndrome. *Nat Med.* 2021;27(4):601–615. DOI: 10.1038/s41591-021-01283-z.
4. Amenta E.M., Spallone A., Rodriguez-Barradas M.C. et al. Post-acute COVID-19: an overview and approach to classification. *Open Forum Infect Dis.* 2020;7(12):ofaa509. DOI: 10.1093/ofid/ofaa509.
5. Arnold D.T., Hamilton F.W., Milne A. et al. Patient outcomes after hospitalisation with COVID-19 and implications for follow-up: results from a prospective UK cohort. *Thorax.* 2021;76:399–401. DOI: 10.1136/thoraxjnl-2020-216086.
6. Chopra V., Flanders S.A., O'Malley M. et al. Sixty-Day Outcomes Among Patients Hospitalized With COVID-19. *Ann Intern Med.* 2021;174(4):576–578. DOI: 10.7326/M20-5661.
7. Halpin S.J., McIvor C., Whyatt G. et al. Post-discharge symptoms and rehabilitation needs in survivors of COVID-19 infection: A cross-sectional evaluation. *J Med Virol.* 2021;93(2):1013–1022. DOI: 10.1002/jmv.26368.
8. Moreno-Pérez O., Merino E., Leon-Ramirez J.M. et al. Post-acute COVID-19 Syndrome incidence and risk factors: a Mediterranean cohort study. *J Infect.* 2021;82(3):378–383. DOI: 10.1016/j.jinf.2021.01.004.
9. Willi S., Lüthold R., Hunt A. et al. COVID-19 sequelae in adults aged less than 50 years: a systematic review. *Travel Med Infect Dis.* 2021;40:101995. DOI: 10.1016/j.tmaid.2021.101995.
10. Carfi A., Bernabei R., Landi F.; Gemelli Against COVID-19 Post-Acute Care Study Group. Persistent Symptoms in Patients After Acute COVID-19. *JAMA.* 2020;324(6):603–605. DOI: 10.1001/jama.2020.12603.
11. Carvalho-Schneider C., Laurent E., Le-maignen A. Follow-up of adults with noncritical COVID-19 two months after symptom onset. *Clin Microbiol Infect.* 2021;27(2):258–263. DOI: 10.1016/j.cmi.2020.09.052.
12. Pavli A., Theodoridou M., Maltezou H.C. Post-COVID syndrome: Incidence, clinical spectrum, and challenges for primary healthcare professionals. *Arch Med Res.* 2021;52(6):575–581. DOI: 10.1016/j.arcmed.2021.03.010.
13. Kozlov I.A., Tyurin I.N. Cardiovascular complications of COVID-19. *Messenger of Anesthesiology and Resuscitation.* 2020;17(4):14–22 (in Russ.). DOI: 10.21292/2078-5658-2020-17-4-14-22.
14. Smirnova E.A., Sedykh E.V. Acute decompensation of heart failure: current issues of epidemiology, diagnostics, therapy. *Science of the young (Eruditio Juvenium).* 2021;9(2):289–300 (in Russ.). DOI: 10.23888/HMJ202192289-300.
15. Aghagoli G., Gallo Marin B., Soliman L.B., Sellke F.W. Cardiac involvement in COVID-19 patients: Risk factors, predictors, and complications: A review. *J Card Surg.* 2020;35(6):1302–1305. DOI: 10.1111/jocs.14538.
16. Chen C., Zhou Y., Wang D.W. SARS-CoV-2: a potential novel etiology of fulminant myocarditis. *Herz.* 2020;45(3):230–232. DOI: 10.1007/s00059-020-04909-z.
17. Kochi A.N., Tagliari A.P., Forleo G.B. et al. Cardiac and arrhythmic complications in patients with COVID-19. *J Cardiovasc Electrophysiol.* 2020;31(5):1003–1008. DOI: 10.1111/jce.14479.
18. Maiti T., Essam L., Orsolini L. et al. COVID-19-induced psychoses: new challenges for aspiring psychiatric careers. *IP Pavlov Russian Medical Biological Herald.* 2021;29(2):325–331 (in Russ.). DOI: 10.17816/PAVLOVJ72035.